

STRUCTURE AND ANALYSIS OF THE MINING SUBSECTOR FROM THE NATIONAL ENERGY SECTOR IN THE CONTEXT OF STABILITY AND INCREASE OF ROMANIAN ENERGY SECURITY

Nicolae Daniel Fiță¹, Sorin Mihai Radu², Roland Iosif Moraru³, Mila Ilieva Obretenova⁴

¹University of Petrosani, Romania; E-mail: daniel.fita@yahoo.com

²University of Petrosani, Romania; E-mail: roland_moraru@yahoo.com

³University of Petrosani, Romania; E-mail: sorin_mihai_radu@yahoo.com

⁴University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, Sofia, Bulgaria; E-mail: mila.ilieva@mgu.bg

Corresponding author: daniel.fita@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT. Until recently, the European Union's energy policy was against coal for pollution reasons, but with the start of the military war between Russia and Ukraine, coal has become one of the energy resources to reconsider. The lack or depletion of oil and natural gas from Russia has made the coal resource the most important source and means to provide energy security. Because there are many coal-fired power stations in Romania (hard coal and lignite), its extraction and recovery becomes a real problem of national security, because it produces electricity, which is vital to Romanian society. The need to analyse the mining subsector, which generates critical mining infrastructure, comes in the context in which the possible occurrence of cases of non-energy supply, or unexpected price increases, generates major issues of national interest, with European and OTAN implications. The aim of the paper is to structure and analyze the mining subsector within the National Energy Sector in the context of stability and increasing national energy security. The authors consider that the approach of the mining subsector is a strictly national security issue because the lack of coal can cause damage to the power sector and the national economy, which are partly dependent on the mining subsector.

Key words: coal, mining subsector, national energy sector, energy security

Energy security issues

The energy security of a state represents (Băhnăreanu, 2008):

- existence, accessibility and supply of finite resources of raw materials (oil, natural gas, coal, hydrocarbons, uranium, etc.) and renewable, sufficient and available;
- clear and stable international / European trade agreements on access to these finite (re)sources of imported raw materials;
- price stability of these finite raw material (re)sources;
- control of transmission and distribution routes and alternatives to finite (re)sources of raw materials;
- the safety and security of the transformation of these finite (re)sources of raw materials into electricity;
- clear and stable trade agreements on trade in electricity with neighboring countries or those of the European Union;
- electricity price stability;
- control of electricity transmission and distribution routes;
- accessibility of each consumer (domestic / industrial) to electricity.

The level of security of a state is given by the ability of that state to aggregate resources internally, to gain and maintain access to external economic resources, and any longer interruption of energy supply has a negative effect on economic growth, political stability and welfare of the citizens of a state (Baumann, 2008).

Energy security plays a very important role in the economic security of a state, for this reason it must be taken in the most serious way, and the failure to attach importance to energy security can cause catastrophic damage with insecurity and instability, endangering the welfare of the people (Ciuta, 2010).

Structure of the national energy sector

The National Energy Sector is composed of the following subsectors: (Figure 1) (Fiță, 2021a).

- Oil subsector:
 - Oil Branch;
 - Natural Gas Branch.
- Nuclear Subsector - Uranium;
- Mining Subsector - Coal;
- Electrical energetic subsector – Electricity.

Fig. 1. Principle of operation and components of the national energy sector

Mining subsector - coal

Generalities regarding the Romanian mining industry

Coal continues to be an important source of energy that can maintain its role as a safe fuel, for many countries being the only fuel available to meet the growing demand for electricity needed to raise living standards. It is very possible that this solid fuel will maintain its share in the global primary energy demand, which is transformed into electricity by using it in thermal power plants.

Romania has almost 200 years of experience in the coal mining industry, and the main national actors in coal mining and extraction are the following:

- Jiu Valley Mining Basin (hard coal – high calorific value coal):
 - Lonea Mine;
 - Livezeni Mine;
 - Vulcan Mine;
 - Lupeni Mine.
- Oltenia Mining Basin (lignite - lower calorific value coal):
 - Roșia – Rovinari open-pit mine;
 - Jił open-pit mine;
 - Motru open-pit mine.

The operating principle of the mining subsector is shown in Figure 2 (Fîță, 2021b).

Fig. 2. The operating principle of the mining subsector

The National Mining System – mining operations

1. Hunedoara Energy Complex:

- geological research for the discovery of coal reserves;
- production, supply and marketing of hardcoal-fired electricity;
- production, dispatching, transport, distribution and supply of thermal energy.

2. Jiu Valley Mine Closing:

- hardcoal extraction;
- mine closing and restoration of affected areas.

3. Oltenia Energy Complex:

- lignite extraction and processing;
- lignite-based electricity and heat generation (Fîță, 2021c)

The complete mining cycle in Romania

Romania currently has rich coal resources (hardcoal and lignite), but the major advantage is that there is a complete mining cycle in the country (Table 1 and Figure 3).

Table 1. Synthesis of the complete mining cycle in Romania

Crt. no.	Stages	Resource type	Operator	Secondary operator
1.	Resource Management	hardcoal / lignite	National Agency for Mineral Resources	
2.	Mining/ Processing/ Transportation	hardcoal	Hunedoara Energy Complex	Lonea, Livezeni, Vulcan, Lupeni Mines
		lignite	Oltenia Energy Complex	Roșia - Rovinari, Jił, Motru Mines
3.	Electricity generation	hardcoal	Hunedoara Energy Complex Jiu Valley Mine Closing	Deva, Paroșeni Thermal Power Stations
		lignite	Oltenia Energy Complex	Rovinari, Turceni, Ișalnița, Craiova II Thermal Power Stations

In order for the mining cycle to be complete through the 3 stages, it is mandatory that all the 3 actors involved are present, namely: (Figure 3) (Fîță, 2021c)

- 1) National Agency for Mineral Resources - which owns the coal resource (hardcoal and lignite);
- 2) Hunedoara Energy Complex/Jiu Valley Mine Closing - which exploits, processes, transports and produces hardcoal-fired electricity;
- 3) Oltenia Energy Complex – which exploits, processes, transports and produces lignite-fired electricity.

Fig. 3. Scheme of the complete mining cycle in Romania

3.4. The mining pressure tool

Definition: Any action or inaction of an actor in the mining energy chain RESOURCE HOLDER (hardcoal / lignite coal) – MINE OPERATOR / PREPARATOR / RESOURCE TRANSPORTER (hardcoal / lignite coal) - ELECTRICITY MANUFACTURER (based on coal or lignite) directly connected to hard coal or lignite resources, which aims to influence the behaviour of other actors, to control or eliminate them, in order to achieve their own interests.

The principle diagram of the use of coal energy resources (hardcoal / lignite) as a pressure tool is shown in Figure 4 (Fîță, 2021b, c).

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of the use of mining energy resources - hardcoal and lignite - as a pressure tool

The pressure tool can be used throughout the chain by any of the "links" involved in this process.

Conclusions

Because coal resources (hardcoal and lignite) are elements of safety and security for those who own them, they can lead to conflicts or energy wars, which are characterised by the use of energy tools to force the opponent to change his policy or behaviour and it undermines the ability of that state to maintain normal relations with other states, in time of peace or war. Without coal resources (hardcoal and lignite), the national economy could suffer as thermoelectric power production is halted, causing huge damage to national industry and energy

security, and energy security is becoming an important component of the national security and external politics. Coal resources can be used as tools of political pressure or energy weapon for profit or economical / political pressure.

The only drawback of coal is air pollution, except gasification, but the costs are enormous. That is why the European Union is against it, but it must be taken into account that it ensures energy security and stability, which is why it is vital.

References

- Băhnăreanu C., 2008. Energy Security, Defense and Security Strategic Studies Center, "Carol I" National Defense University Publishing House, Bucharest.
- Baumann F., 2008, Energy security as multidimensional concept, CAP Policy Analysis, 1, 4-5.
- Ciuta F., 2010. Conceptual Notes on Energy Security: Total or Banal Security?, Security Dialogue, 41 (2), 123-144, www.jstor.org/stable/26301149
- Fîță N. D., Radu S. M., Păsculescu D., Popescu F. G., 2021a, Using the primary energetic resources or electrical energy as a possible energetical tool or pressure tool, Proceedings of Sciendo International Conference Knowledge based organisation – "Nicolae Balcescu" Land Forced Academy Sibiu 2021, v. XXVII, no. 3, .21-26, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2478/kbo-2021-0084>,
- Fîță N. D., Radu, S.M., Păculescu, D. 2021b, Ensuring, controlling and stability of energy security in the context of increasing industrial and national security – Academic Compendium, Universitas Publishing House, Petroșani, ISBN 978-973-741-743-5,
- Fîță N. D., Radu S. M., Păsculescu D., Gregory E., 2021c, The approach of national critical energy infrastructures correlated with societal resilience and sustainability, in: Sustainability management and managerial sustainability between classical and modern paradigms, ed. D. E. Ranf, O. M. C. Bucovetchi, D. Badea, Publishing house of the Academy of Land Forces "Nicolae Bălcescu" Sibiu, Romania, ISBN 978-973-153-419, 37 – 58.